

MAHALLIY BYUDJET DAROMADLARIGA INVESTITSUYALARNING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Surxondaryo viloyatida mahalliy byudjeti daromadlariga asosiy kapitalga o'zlashtirilgan investitsiyalarning ta'siri ekonometrik tadqiq etilgan. Natijada avtoregressiya modeli tuzish orqali qisqa va uzoq muddatli multiplikatorlar qiymatlari aniqlanib, xulosalar qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: model, avtoregressiya, regressiya tenglamasi, styudent, t mezoni, Fisher, instrumental o'zgaruvchi.

Mahalliy byudjet daromadlar bazasini shakllantirishda unga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning ta'sir darajasini baholash alohida ahamiyatga ega. Bunda ekonometrik modellardan foydalanish nafaqat istiqboldagi byudjet tushumlari, balki omillarning ta'sir darajalarini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Tadqiqot uchun 2010-2023 yillardagi Surxondaryo viloyati byudjet daromadlari¹ hamda asosiy kapitalga o'zlashtirilgan investitsiyalar² hajmi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar 1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

1-jadval

Surxondaryo viloyati kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik ishlab chiqarish hajmi va asosiy kapitalga o'zlashtirilgan investitsiyalar hajmi qiymatlari³

Yillar	Surxondaryo viloyati byudjet daromadlari, mlrd so'm	Asosiy kapitalga o'zlashtirilgan investitsiyalar, mlrd so'm
<i>n</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>x</i>

¹ To'rayev, B. E. (2024). Mahalliy byudjet daromadlarini ARIMA modeli asosida prognozlash. Journal of Universal Science Research, 2(1), 141-149.

² www.surxonstat.uz – Surxondaryo viloyat Statistika boshqarmasi rasmiy sayti ma'lumotlari.

³ www.surxonstat.uz – Surxondaryo viloyat Statistika boshqarmasi rasmiy sayti ma'lumotlari.

2010	264	655,3
2011	351,6	802,9
2012	413,9	980,3
2013	514,9	1371,0
2014	571,7	1509,1
2015	699,1	1843,6
2016	835,5	2142,4
2017	969,8	3551,0
2018	1052,1	7240,6
2019	1844,7	11835,1
2020	1605,7	10068,2
2021	1993,2	12037,8
2022	2466,9	11569,4
2023*	2 962,8	17956,0

Investitsiyalarning mahalliy byudjet daromadlari hajmiga ta’sirini baholashda avtoregressiya modellari istiqboldagi qisqa va uzoq muddatli o’zgarishlar darajalarini aniqlash imkonini beradi. $AR(1) + x$ ko’rinishidagi avtoregressiya modeli umumiy ko’rinishi quyidagicha:

$$y_t = a + b_0 \cdot x_t + c_1 \cdot y_{t-1} + e_t \tag{1}$$

Ushbu modelni hisoblash uchun dastlab instrumental o’zgaruvchini baholovchi model tuzish talab etiladi:

$$\hat{y}_{t-1} = d_0 + d_1 \cdot x_{t-1} \tag{2}$$

(2) modelni baholash uchun lag o’zgaruvchilar qiymatlari 2-jadvalda berilgan.

2-jadval

Surxondaryo viloyati mahalliy byudjet daromadlari hajmi va asosiy kapitalga o'zlashtirilgan investitsiyalar hajmi ko'rsatkichlarning $t - 1$ davrdagi qiymatlari⁴

Yillar	y_t	x_t	y_{t-1}	x_{t-1}
2010	264	655,3	-	-
2011	351,6	802,9	264	655,3
2012	413,9	980,3	351,6	802,9
2013	514,9	1371,0	413,9	980,3
2014	571,7	1509,1	514,9	1370,992
2015	699,1	1843,6	571,7	1509,144
2016	835,5	2142,4	699,1	1843,612
2017	969,8	3551,0	835,5	2142,412
2018	1052,1	7240,6	969,8	3551
2019	1844,7	11835,1	1052,1	7240,6
2020	1605,7	10068,2	1844,7	11835,07
2021	1993,2	12037,8	1605,7	10068,2
2022	2466,9	11569,4	1993,2	12037,76
2023	2 962,8	17956,0	2466,9	11569,4

Microsoft Excel dasturining «Анализ данных» paketidan foydalanib 2-jadvaldagi ma'lumotlarning regression bog'lanishini ko'rib chiqamiz (3-jadval).

3-jadval

Regression tahlil natijalari⁵

**ВЫВОД
ИТОГОВ**

⁴ Surxondaryo viloyati Statistika boshqarmasi www.surxonstat.uz sayti

⁵ Muallif ishlanmasi

<i>Регрессионная статистика</i>					
Множественный R		0,958			
R-квадрат		0,917			
Нормированный R-квадрат		0,910			
Стандартная ошибка		212,871			
Наблюдения		13			
<i>Дисперсионный анализ</i>					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Значимость F</i>
Регрессия	1	5539643,583	5539643,583	122,249	2,68616E-07
Остаток	11	498456,7493	45314,24994		
Итого	12	6038100,32			
	<i>Коэффициенты</i>	<i>Стандартная ошибка</i>	<i>t-статистика</i>	<i>P-Значение</i>	<i>Нижние 95%</i>
Y-пересечение	319,716	88,244	3,623	0,004	125,492
Переменная X 1	0,144	0,013	11,057	0,000	0,115

\hat{y}_{t-1} instrumental o'zgaruvchini aniqlovchi regressiya tenglamasining umumiy ko'rinishi

$$\hat{y}_{t-1} = 319,716 + 0,144 \cdot x_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

Ushbu (3) model bo'yicha Fisherning F mezonining hisoblangan qiymati $F_{his} = 1013,663$ ga teng, bu esa $df_1 = m = 1$ va $df_2 = n - 1 - 1 = 12$ erkinlik darajasida hamda, $\alpha = 0,05$ ahamiyatlilik darajasida Fisherning jadval qiymati $F_{jad} = 4.75$ dan katta. Shuningdek (3) modelning parametrlari bo'yicha Styudentning t mezon qiymatlari $t_{d_0} = 2,882$ hamda $t_{d_1} = 10,083$ ga teng, bu esa $\alpha = 0,05$ ahamiyatlilik darajasida hamda $df = n - m = 13$ erkinlik darajasida Styudentning $t_{jad} = 2,16$ dan katta. Shu sababli model statistik ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi.

\hat{y}_{t-1} instrumental o'zgaruvchining nazariy qiymatlarini aniqlaymiz. (4-jadval).

4-jadval

Instrumental o'zgaruvchining nazariy qiymatlari⁶

Yillar	y_t	x_t	y_{t-1}	x_{t-1}	\hat{y}_{t-1}
2010	264	655,3	-	-	-
2011	351,6	802,9	264	655,3	413,9
2012	413,9	980,3	351,6	802,9	435,1
2013	514,9	1371,0	413,9	980,3	460,6
2014	571,7	1509,1	514,9	1370,992	516,7
2015	699,1	1843,6	571,7	1509,144	536,6
2016	835,5	2142,4	699,1	1843,612	584,6
2017	969,8	3551,0	835,5	2142,412	627,6
2018	1052,1	7240,6	969,8	3551	829,9
2019	1844,7	11835,1	1052,1	7240,6	1 360,1
2020	1605,7	10068,2	1844,7	11835,07	2 020,3
2021	1993,2	12037,8	1605,7	10068,2	1 766,4
2022	2466,9	11569,4	1993,2	12037,76	2 049,4
2023	2 962,8	17956,0	2466,9	11569,4	1 982,1

⁶ Surxondaryo viloyati Statistika boshqarmasi www.surxonstat.uz sayti

4-jadvaldagi y_t , x_t hamda \hat{y}_{t-1} o'zgaruvchilar ishtirokida (1) modelni baholadik. Buning uchun yana Microsoft excel imkoniyatlaridan foydalandik. Biroq (1) model parametrlari statistik ahamiyatga ega bo'lmadi. Shu sababli (1) modelni o'zgarms ishtirokisiz baholadik (5-jadval).

3-jadval

Regression tahlil natijalari⁷

ВЫВОД
ИТОГОВ

<i>Регрессионная статистика</i>	
Множественный R	0,990
R-квадрат	0,979
Нормированный R-квадрат	0,887
Стандартная ошибка	233,097
Наблюдения	13

Дисперсионный анализ

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Значимость F</i>
Регрессия	2	28341349,36	14170674,68	260,806	2,35521E-09
Остаток	11	597676,645	54334,2404		
Итого	13	28939026			

⁷ Muallif ishlanmasi

	Коэффициенты	Стандартная ошибка	t-статистика	P-Значение	Нижние 95%
Y-пересечение	0,000	#Н/Д	#Н/Д	#Н/Д	#Н/Д
Переменная X 1	0,091	0,028	3,264	0,008	0,030
Переменная X 2	0,587	0,191	3,071	0,011	0,166

Bundan avtoregressiya tenglamamiz:

$$y_t = 0,091x_t + 0,587y_{t-1} \quad (4)$$

ko‘rinishga ega bo‘ladi. Model barcha parametrlari hamda modelning o‘zi statistic ahamiyatga ega.

Shunday qilib, (4) modelga ko‘ra qisqa muddatli multiplikator $b_0 = 0,091$ ga teng, ya‘ni x_t - asosiy kapitalga o‘zlashtirilgan investitsiyalar hajmining 1 mlrd so‘mga ortishi y_t - mahalliy byudjet daromadlarini o‘rtacha 0,091 mlrd so‘mga oshiradi. Uzoq muddatli multiplikator $b = \frac{b_0}{1-c} = \frac{0,091}{1-0,587} = 0,22072$ ga teng, ya‘ni x_t ning 1 mlrd so‘mga oshishi esa, y_t ni uzoq muddatda 0,22072 mlrd so‘mga oshiradi.

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